

Facile synthesis of Room temperature LPG sensor based on Nano structured composite of Graphene oxide and SnO₂ anchored with PANI.

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Abstract

In this present work, a LPG sensor based on ternary nano- hybrid of (PANI–SnO₂/GO) has been synthesized via wet chemical route. The crystal structure, Morphologies and composite are examined by various characterizations techniques such as UV-Visible spectroscopy, X-Ray diffraction, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, and Scanning electron microscope. The gas sensing behavior of the nano composite were analyzed by exposing different ppm at room temperature. The composite shows good sensitivity towards the flow of LPG and it has improved response and recovery time. This composite have selective towards LPG against oxygen and hydrogen. The addition of conducting polymer PANI in the ternary structures modulates the electron transfer between the composite towards the gas molecules at room temperature. This synthesized composite has promising advantages in the field of gas sensor by means of reduced operating temperature ease of fabrication and low cost.

Keywords : Ternary hybrid, Gas sensor, Nano structured Composites, LPG Sensor